

THE HEALING PROPERTIES OF LEMON LEAVES AS SOME FOOD RICH IN VITAMINS.

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Abstract:

Nutritional value, its significance for food rations and benefits of lemon leaves to the human body. It is indicated that locally grown lemon leaves can be dried and processed in the food industry.

Key words: virus, bitter orange, citrus, deficiency, skin, seasoning, lemon leaves, preservation, essential oils.

INTRODUCTION

The founder of medicine, the great Avicenna, has such a wise hypothesis: "Looking at your diet, you can tell who you are and what you are capable of." This indicates that human nutrition has a lot of importance for his mental and physical activity, working capacity. The diversity of the human diet, adding spices to improve their taste and usefulness with processed local raw materials is highly effective. This type of product is provided not only by our market, but we will be able to offer high-quality goods to the world market.

Globally, the viability of viruses and single-celled microorganisms has increased, as we have seen with the example of the corona virus. Many scientists have proven that by increasing human immunity, it is possible to fight such infections and viruses. In order to increase human immunity and strengthen it, one of the important issues is to increase the diversity of the human diet and enrich them with vitamins, minerals and enzymes through biologically active additives. The production of food additives and semi-finished products rich in vitamins and minerals for food purposes from available local agricultural and flora resources is a vital necessity. In addition, a source of medicinal raw materials is available in most of our republic. To a large extent, our country is experiencing a shortage in citrus essential oils of spices, which are made from lemon leaves to fish, seafood, which are widely distributed in our diet.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Lemon is not found in this nature. There is an assumption by scientists that the plants appeared as a result of cross-pollination of bitter orange and citron, it happened many thousands of years ago on the territory of China, India and the islands of the Pacific region.

Botanists believe that cultivated citrus species are complex cultigen complexes that arose as a result of centuries-old breeding of the original wild-growing, now extant forms. The features of citrus fruits include their longevity; their average life expectancy is more than 100 years. The leaves of citrus trees live for 2-3 years and will change gradually (hence the name of these plants - evergreen).

Currently, up to 15 organic acids have been found in lemon fruits, among them aconite, chromogenic, citramalic, galacturonic, quick, and isolimonic, which is consistent with the fact that all enzymes of the tricarboxylic acid cycle have been found in lemon fruits, which carry out mutual transformations of organic acids. In recent years, evidence has accumulated that organic acids in lemon fruits are synthesized in juice sacs inside the fruit, in addition to the previously existing view that acids accumulating in fruits are formed mainly in leaves. Lemon leaves last longer than the leaves of other plants, leaf fall occurs once every three years, which indicates that lemon leaves are resistant to environmental changes and are rich in vitamins and trace elements. Scientific studies of citrus fruits have revealed their antioxidant, anti-carcinogenic, anti-allergenic, antiviral and other beneficial properties. Hippocrates, Avicenna and others also used them as an effective remedy. Citrus fruits are also popular in modern folk medicine, as the fragrant product is useful and rich in vitamins and is widely used in public nutrition.

Lemon leaves are fragrant, dark green and shiny, and are useful in many applications. Since they are non-toxic, they can be widely used, including in cooking, confectionery, you can also brew crushed dry leaves and drink them as tea. If you have the opportunity to grow a lemon tree, you will be pleasantly surprised to discover how many ways there are for people to use.

Lemon leaves whiten the skin of the face, they can also be used in cosmetology. In Italy, festive garlands and wedding bouquets of the bride are made from fresh lemon leaves. At the same time, Uzbekistan belongs to the large consumers of lemon, whose peel is rich in essential oils, and the leaves contain

more than vitamin C, organic acids, than the fruit itself. Lemon leaves have a restorative property. When used, they are able to improve the general condition of the body, tone up and increase resistance to various viral diseases. There are practically no contraindications to taking it. It is only necessary to use the leaves with caution during pregnancy, and also do not use this product for allergies and individual intolerance.

Table 1

Useful and medicinal properties of lemon leaves

Chemical composition	Useful properties	Medicinal properties
Vitamin C (ascorbic acid)The content is 14 times higher than in fruits	-Has an antimicrobial effect -Plays an important role in the body's absorption of vitamins and trace elements.	-Improves the functioning of the digestive system - is a participant in redox processes
Vitamin A (retinol)	- Positive effects on eyesight -A powerful antioxidant	-Strengthens the immune system - protects against infections of the respiratory, genitourinary tract, digestive tract and flu. --Facilitates the course of chickenpox, measles, AIDS -Restores the skin, mucous membrane for psoriasis, burns, wounds, pimples
Vitamin B	- It participates in cell growth and energy exchange. -Strengthens the immune system	-Normalizes the functioning of the cardiovascular and nervous systems. -Used during stress, depression, emotional overload
Vitamin P (rutin)	-Increases the efficiency	-Reduces the fragility of

	of useful elements -Strengthens the immune system	capillaries -protects against fungi, parasites, and dangerous bacteria. -effective for hypertension , varicose veins
Essential oils: terpenes, citrates, a-limonene, geranyl acetate	--Improve performance, invigorates, relieves fatigue -Cleanses the respiratory tract of pathogenic bacteria and viruses --as an antispasmodic, it eliminates spasms, pain helps to relieve tension from the muscles. It helps with rheumatism.	-Used in aromatherapy during inhalations and massages --it has an antispasmodic, vasodilation effect on the bronchi. -antioxidant effect protects lipids from oxidation. anti-inflammatory and analgesic

In many cultures, lemon leaves are widely used in cooking. They can be used fresh, as well as dried, ground and used as a seasoning. Such a recipe for cooking a dish is in the diet of many peoples of the world. Lemon leaves are added to various marinades, used in preservation, as well as in the preparation of various dishes, adding piquancy to them.

By steam distillation, petitgrain lemon oil is obtained from the leaves of young branches and unripe fruits of the Citrus Limon Burm lemon tree with a yield of about 0.2%. The oil is greenish-yellow to olive in color, with a bitter slightly herbaceous and woody aroma. The aromatic qualities of petitgray and lemon are determined along with citral by the presence of nerol and neryl acetate. Due to the presence of these components, the oil has a lemon-pink smell.

The chemical composition of this oil is not similar to that of lemon peel oil. Among 68% of monoterpene hydrocarbons, 39% of limonene and 19% of beta-pinene were found. The presence of citral (16%), citronellal (0.9%), methylheptenone (2.3%), geraniol and nerol (3.8% in total), as well as geranyl acetate was established (2,6%)

Table 2

Lemon Petitgrain essential oil contains

Nº	The name of the ethers	mg/kg leaves	%
1	a-thuyen	0,84	0,11
2	a-pinene	10,8	1,38
3	camphere	0,78	0,10
4	β -pinene	101,6	13,01
5	myrcene	17,3	2,22
6	a-terpinene	1,4	0,18
7	Δ^3 -karen	10,4	1,33
8	limonene	167,0	21,39
9	(Z)- β -ocimene	4,7	0,60
10	(E)- β -ocimene	23,7	3,04
11	y-terpinene	3,7	0,47
12	terpinolene	2,6	0,33
13	linalone	12,1	1,55
14	nonanol	2,1	0,27
15	citronellan	16,4	2,10
16	isocitral	3,77	0,48
17	usocitral	3,8	0,49
18	terpinen 4	4,9	0,63
19	a-terpinol	5,8	0,74
20	dekanol	0,8	0,10
21	okticellete	48	6,15
22	nerale	121,9	15,53
23	geraniale	109,4	14,01
24	undecanale	0,9	0,12
25	citronellicitate	2,8	0,36
26	nerilacitat	55,7	7,13
27	geranilacitate	35,4	4,53
28	β -kariofillene	6,9	0,88
29	dodekanale	0,60	0,08
30	transferol	0,77	0,10
31	a-gumulene	1,8	0,23

32	nerillopropiocitat	1,21	0,15
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Results.In natural ways, the cultivated crop is well tolerated by the human body, vitamins and minerals are well absorbed, given all this, we can fully consider lemon leaves a useful product for everyday use as a food additive in the form of seasoning, as tea and salads can be added in general. The head of the medical center "Magic of Health" Karomatov I. J. in his articles pointed out a number of useful properties of citrus fruits, he calls citrus fruits as medicinal products.

Lemon leaves contain about 14 times more vitamin C than fruits, 880 milligrams. In addition, they also contain vitamins A, B and P, and a large amount of essential oil (Table 2).

Lemon leaves are very useful for the human body, they have many positive properties antibacterial, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, immune-boosting, choleric, astringent. Lemon leaves have a restorative property, when used they are able to improve the general condition of the body, tone up and increase resistance to various viral diseases. Contraindications to taking lemon leaves do not register in medical literature, there are practically no side effects. All ancient healers Galen, Hippocrates, Avicenna and others wrote about the healing properties of lemon. The use of leaves in cooking, even in small quantities, helps to strengthen the immune system, tone the body and restore strength. Lemon leaves give the dishes a slightly astringent, spicy, refreshing taste. Lemon leaves can be used as a seasoning in fresh and dried, frozen form. They can be added to hot dishes of meat, cereals, vegetables, seafood, fish, marinades, canned food, beverages, confectionery products. Lemon leaves combine very well with all kinds of seasonings gives an aromatic taste and smell improves the taste of food the vitamin complex in the leaves increases the usefulness of food.

In the cuisines of the Mediterranean region, there are recipes in which lemon leaves are used to wrap and bake minced meat or fish. Lemon leaves give the dishes a slightly astringent, spicy, refreshing taste. They can be added to almost everything to drinks, tea, salads, sauce, various soups, various meats, fish, they improve the quality and flavor of food.

The use of cooking, even in small quantities, helps to strengthen the immune system, tone the body and restore strength. Lemon leaves act as a traditional seasoning in the regions where citrus trees grow in Asia, southern Europe, and Mexico.

Conclusions. Currently, our republic, as a rule, uses only the fruits themselves, and substandard fruits and peel. The leaves are considered as waste that needs to be disposed of. Complex processing of lemon peel and leaves expediently solves the shortage of essential oils, seasonings of fish processing enterprises, public nutrition, complements a number of dietary supplements. The organization of complex processing of the entire biomass of lemon fruits will help reduce import dependence for a number of industries, increase the competitiveness of goods and get rid of some household waste. An effective option is the processing of lemon waste, leaves at enterprises where fresh lemon juice is used for their products. The remaining squeezes can serve as a raw material for obtaining essential oil, and lemon leaves can be dried or crushed fresh, added to seasonings, it is possible to produce dietary supplements in tea bags. You can add fresh leaves to tea instead of a slice of lemon, it will turn out to be just as tasty and fragrant. The rules of rational human nutrition emphasize that the consumption of traditional green tea in our country with meat and vegetable foods slows down the absorption of iron. You can eliminate such an incorrect way of eating by replacing green tea with dry tea made from lemon leaves, rich in vitamins. The high content of vitamin C B. contained in tea made from dried lemon leaves prevents the formation of blood clots. The results of the research serve as the basis for the organization in our republic of small-scale production from lemon leaves, from lemon squeezes of essential oil and citrus mass formed as waste, which are ingredients of confectionery products. Their production serves as the final process of processing lemon biomass, the only product used of which was only juice. In addition to waste disposal, the introduction allows you to replace the synthetic essence used with natural essential oil and expand the range of products produced.

References:

1. Зубайдова Т.М., Нуралиев Ю.Н., Ганиев Х.А., Самандаров Н.Ю. Механизм действия кислых продуктов в развитии предиабета в остром эксперименте - Вестник Таджикского Национального Университета. Серия естественных наук 2013, 1-3, 105-108.
2. Кароматов И.Д. Простые лекарственные средства Бухара 2012.
3. Кароматов И.Д., Бадриддинова М.Н. Сочетание фитопрепаратов с современным медикаментами (обзор литературы - Современная наука - обществу XXI века. Книга 2 Ставрополь «Логос» 2015, глава VI, 181-202.
4. «Лимон мифы и реальность». Неумывакин. И-2010г

5. Лекарственные растения :Энциклопедический справочник /под редакции А.М.Гроздинского.-К.Олимп-1992,стр 544
6. Абу Али ибн Сино Канон врачебной науки II том Ташкент, 1996.
7. Амасиацы А. Ненужное для неучей М., Наука 1990.
8. Гетко Н.В., Алехна А.И., Субоч В.П., Почицкая И.М., Титок В.В. Состав летучих компонентов листьев гибридов и сортов лимона (Citrus X Limon (L.) Burn.F.), культивируемых в оранжерее - Вестник Нацыянальнай Акадэмі Навук Беларусь Серыя Біялагічных Навук 2014, 2, 5-10.
9. Зоҳдцов Х. Канзи шифо - Душанбе Ирфон 1991.
10. Мишарина Т.А., Теренина М.Б., Крикунова Н.И., Медведева И.Б. Антиоксидантные свойства эфирных масел лимона - Все материалы. Энциклопедический справочник 2009, 7, 35-40.
11. Нуралиев Ю.Н., Ганиев Х.А., Зубайдова Т.М., Самандаров Н.Ю. О предиабетогенном действии сока лимона Citrus Limon (L) -Вестник последипломного образования в сфере здравоохранения 2011, 4, 33-35.
12. Турчина Е.Г., Сидоров Е.П. Влияние продуктов питания на биологический возраст мужчин - Вестник Российского Университета Дружбы Народов. Серия: Экология и безопасность жизнедеятельности 2015, 4, 131-136.
13. Холов А.К., Азонов Д.А. Эфиромасличные растения и эфирные масла - источники биологически активных веществ (обзор литературы) - Вестник Таджикского Национального Университета. Серия Естественных Наук 2014, 1-3, 153-160.
14. Чупахина Г.Н., Масленников П.В., Скрыпник Л.Н., Федурев П.В., Чупахина Н.Ю. Антиоксидантные свойства плодов лимона - Антиоксидантные свойства культурных растений Калининградской области - Калининград, 2016, 88-89.
13. Abdelkawy K.S., Donia A.M., Turner R.B., Elbarbry F. Effects of Lemon and Seville Orange Juices on the Pharmacokinetic Properties of Sildenafil in Healthy Subjects - Drugs R. D. 2016, Sep., 16(3), 271-278.
14. Adeniyi O.S., Omale J., Omeje S.C., Edino V.O. Antidiarrheal activity of hexane extract of Citrus limon peel in an experimental animal model - J. Integr. Med. 2017, Mar., 15(2), 158-164.
15. Ahmad M., Ansari M.N., Alam A., Khan T.H. Oral dose of citrus peel extracts promotes wound repair in diabetic rats - Pak. J. Biol. Sci. 2013, Oct 15, 16(20), 1086-1094.

16. Alam M.A., Subhan N., Rahman M.M., Uddin S.J., Reza H.M., Sarker S.D. Effect of citrus flavonoids, naringin and naringenin, on metabolic syndrome and their mechanisms of action - *Adv. Nutr.* 2014, Jul 14, 5(4), 404-417.
17. Alshatwi A.A., Shafi G., Hasan T.N., Al-Hazzani A.A., Alsaif M.A., Alfawaz M.A., Lei K.Y., Munshi A. Apoptosis-mediated inhibition of human breast cancer cell proliferation by lemon citrus extract - *Asian. Pac. J. Cancer. Prev.* 2011, 12(6), 1555-1559.
18. Aslani N., Entezari M.H., Askari G., Maghsoudi Z., Maracy M.R. Effect of Garlic and Lemon Juice Mixture on Lipid Profile and Some Cardiovascular Risk Factors in People 30-60 Years Old with Moderate Hyperlipidaemia: A Randomized Clinical Trial - *Int. J. Prev. Med.* 2016, Jul 29, 7, 95.

